

Bio-based vanillin alcohol diglycidyl ether (DGEVA)-silica coatings for corrosion protection of AA2024

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ABSTRACT

Background: Currently, 75% of global epoxy polymers are based on bisphenol A (BPA), a substance identified as reprotoxic, posing challenges to the development of eco-friendly epoxy coatings.

Methods: Our study reports the synthesis of three novel bio-based anti-corrosion coatings composed of vanillin alcohol diglycidyl ether (DGEVA) and silica nanoparticles, which were added to improve the adhesion to AA2024 substrates.

Findings: The coatings present high adhesion (~7 MPa) and excellent thermal stability (>295 °C), besides good corrosion protection of the hybrid coating (impedance modulus of ~4 MΩ cm⁻² in 3.5 wt% NaCl for > 68 days). The results reveal that proper silica distribution fosters adhesion and extends lifespan via metal oxide-polymer bonds.

1. Introduction

Epoxy coatings are widely used for corrosion protection of automotive and aeronautic alloys. However, about 75 % of them are composed of Diglycidylether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) derived from bisphenol A (BPA) [1], known as an endocrine disruptor with harmful effects on the reproductive system [2]. Replacing DGEBA is a real challenge to tackle due to its exceptional crosslinking, mechanical and thermal properties [3]. Although attempts have been made to substitute DGEBA with bio-based alternatives such as Jatropa-oil-based epoxy acrylate [4], epoxy resin diglycidyl ether of glycerol [5] and bioethanol fractionated lignin [6], their corrosion protection efficiency is not yet comparable to that of traditional DGEBA coatings [7]. Vanillin alcohol diglycidyl ether (DGEVA), a compound obtained from wood dust, has emerged as an attractive alternative to DGEBA due to its excellent thermo-mechanical properties (thermal stability of 335 °C at 5 % weight loss, phase transition (T_g) from 140 to 200 °C and glass transition temperature (T_g) of 152 °C) [8].

Previous research demonstrated that incorporating inorganic precursors, such as silica, extended the service life of micrometric polymer

coatings to more than two years [9]. Here, we explore three synthesis routes using different sources of silica to enhance adhesion and cross-linking of DGEVA polymer chains on AA2024 alloy. Despite its promising properties, DGEVA has not been reported in anti-corrosion applications, nor modified with silica, making this eco-friendly DGEVA-silica coating an innovative solution to DGEBA due to its hybrid and green nature, high adhesion, and cost-effectiveness.

2. Experimental

Vanillin alcohol diglycidyl ether (DGEVA), 3 Glycidyoxypropyl trimethoxysilane (GPTMS) and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) were employed as the monomer, coupling molecules and silica precursors. Diethylenetriamine (DETA) was used as the curing agent. The synthesis parameters were optimized in terms of the hardener-to-monomer ratio, similarly to [10]. Three coatings (Fig. 1a) were designed in this work:

- 1) Primer: 4.08 mL of TEOS + 2.84 mL of ethanol + 1.73 mL of acidified water (HNO₃, pH 1) composed the sol. The sol was mixed for one hour at room temperature (RT, 24 ± 2 °C) and deposited on AA2024

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Fig. 1. A) three synthesis processes; b) coated aa2024 and freestanding coating; c) reaction mechanisms of DGEVA-silica.

by dip coating. After drying at RT, a hybrid organic–inorganic sol (2.13 g of DGEVA + 1.76 mL of GPTMS + 0.10 mL of DETA mixed for 1.5 h in a reflux system at 55 °C) was deposited on top of the primer.

- Hybrid: A sol composed of TEOS/EtOH/H₂O mixed for 1.5 h at pH 3.5 was added dropwise to the hybrid organic–inorganic sol prepared in process 1.
- Nanoparticles: 0.52 mL of Ludox® 40 % (colloidal suspension, approx. size 40 nm) was incorporated into the hybrid organic–inorganic sol prepared in process 1.

All coatings were applied on AA2024 by dip coating (Fig. 1b), 3 immersions (28.4 cm/min) for one minute followed by one 3-minute of drying. Acetone (5 mL) was the solvent in all compositions, resulting in an entirely green coating. Coated AA2024 specimens and remaining solutions were dried at 60 °C for 24 h, 80 °C for 17 h, 100 °C for 2 h and 120 °C for 2 h, ensuring complete polymerization of the coatings (Fig. 1c).

The coated AA2024 were immediately characterized after synthesis by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), once potential stability was achieved, using a Gamry Potentiostat Reference 600, with frequency ranging from 5 mHz to 1 MHz, 10 points per decade, amplitude of 10 mV (rms). The coated substrates served as working electrodes (0.8 cm², O-ring), the saturated 3 M KCl electrode as the reference electrode, a platinum wire (Ø 0.3 mm) as a counter electrode and 3.5 wt % NaCl solution was employed as the electrolyte. EIS data were fitted with Zview® (Scribner Associates) using electrical equivalent circuits (EECs).

Subsequent structural analysis took approximately three months. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed on freestanding coatings (Fig. 1b) using Perkin Elmer Spectrum 100 (4000 – 400 cm⁻¹) with 4 cm⁻¹ resolution and 64 s scan time. Thermal stability was assessed via TGA (Setaram Setsys S60/58341) by heating 7 mg of monoliths from 25 to 600 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ under nitrogen flow (100 mL min⁻¹). Gold sputtered cross sections were examined by SEM (JEOL JSM7600) to determine coating thickness. AFM (Nanotec Electronic) determined roughness, with root-mean-square (R_{RMS}) calculated from

three AFM maps (5 μm²) using Gwyddion software. Water contact angle (WCA) was measured with a Kruss DSA 100 system (5 μL probing liquid, RT, ~43 % RH, average of three measurements). Coating's adhesion of triplicates was obtained using an Elcometer 510 Automatic pull-off Adhesion Gauge applying increasing tensile force at a 0.8 MPa/s rate, in addition to a Cross Hatch Adhesion Tester (Neutrek Instruments) following the ISO 2409. Coating removal was classified from 0B to 5B, with higher numbers indicating better adhesion.

3. Results and discussion

Curing of DGEVA resin and GPTMS was followed by FTIR through the disappearance of the characteristic peak of DGEVA at 916 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C of the oxirane group) [11]. Fig. 2a demonstrates its complete disappearance in NPs and primer coatings, but a small peak persists in the hybrid coating, suggesting the need for a longer reaction time or incomplete condensation of silica. Stretching of ether groups (C–O–C) at 1037 cm⁻¹ indicates epoxy ring opening in the presence of amines, particularly pronounced in NPs. Conversely, the C–C–O–C vibrations at 1182 cm⁻¹ present a similar profile for all three coatings [10].

Thermogravimetric analysis in nitrogen atmosphere reveals thermal stability above 295 °C, of all freestanding DGEVA-silica coatings, with the NPs exhibiting the highest stability (Fig. 2c – 2d, 3e). TGA identifies four main degradation events (Fig. 2e): dehydration (~100 °C), C–C and C–O bond breakage (~200 °C), and N–C bond cleavage (~350 °C), with SiO₂ formation above > 550 °C [10]. The purely organic DGEVA coating on top of the Primer approximately halved the residue (Fig. 2c, 3e). While NPs contributed to a more uniform polymer chain formation, the hybrid coating's higher inorganic residue (48 %) likely affected epoxy ring curing (Fig. 2a).

The coating's dry thickness ranged from 3 to 5 μm, increasing in the order of hybrid < nanoparticles < primer. WCA measurements indicate the hydrophilic nature of the coatings: both primer and hybrid coatings exhibit similar WCA values (56° and 50°). The incorporation of NPs increases the surface roughness and the WCA to 72°. AFM 3D maps showed that the hybrid and primer coatings filled AA2024 grooves

Fig. 2. A-b) FTIR spectra of DGEVA, NPs, hybrid and primer coatings; c) TGA and d) dTG of DGEVA-silica; e) schematic depiction of thermal degradation events of DGEVA.

Fig. 3. WCA, AFM 3D images, pull-off values and cross-cut images of a) uncoated AA2024, b) hybrid, c) primer and d) nanoparticles; e) Properties of the coatings.

Fig. 4. EIS plots of AA2024 and DGEVA-silica coatings prepared with a) NPs, b) primer and c) hybrid methodologies, indicating failure events with red arrows. EECs and corresponding parameters are shown in (d-e).

(R_{RMS} 37 nm), lowering roughness to around 25 nm (Fig. 3e). Pull-off adhesion tests (bar graph) show values of about 7.5 MPa with a slight decrease for NPs (~7.0). These results are in line with the surface cross-cutting tests ranging from 4B for NPs to 5B for primer and hybrid coatings.

EIS measurements in 3.5 wt% NaCl solution showed good protection for all coatings after 2 h (black curves), with impedance values about three orders of magnitude higher than uncoated AA2024. The incorporation of NPs improved the cross-linking of the polymer structure and epoxy ring curing; however, the ~40 nm NPs compromised the structure and coating's adhesion [10], leading to poor corrosion protection and pitting formation after only four days (Fig. 4a). The primer system (Fig. 4b) improved adhesion, but after 30 days, pit formation allowed electrolyte ingress. Interestingly, EIS plots and extracted EEC parameters reveal enhanced barrier properties without failure over 68 days for the hybrid coating (Fig. 4c, 4d). Different EECs were employed for different stages of coating's degradation: in addition to the solution

resistance (R_s), two time constants (R/CPE) represented the resistance and capacitance of a layer with pores and a third time constant was added when the coatings failed, due to pitting corrosion (Fig. 4e). The corrosion resistance of the hybrid coating inner layer (R_{in}) decreased from 11.3 to 2.8 $\text{M}\Omega \text{cm}^2$ after 68 days, as shown in Fig. 4d, whereas Primer and NPs resistance was determined to be as low as 0.28 and 0.08 $\text{M}\Omega \text{cm}^2$, after 4 and 30 days, respectively. This stable barrier against water and ion permeation (Hybrid) results from a proper polymer-silica ratio and homogeneous distribution [7,9].

4. Conclusions

The modification of DGEVA with commercial silica nanoparticles (NPs) or silica sols in the form of a hybrid system or a primer yielded thin (3–5 μm), adhesive (~7 MPa, 5B), and green DGEVA-silica coatings. Primer and NPs coatings show a complete opening of the oxirane ring, with high thermal stability, reaching its maximum for the NPs (334 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The results demonstrate the crucial role of silica in the formation of an interconnected network. Adhesion tests confirmed that the primer and hybrid system foster covalent bonds on AA2024, without mechanical failure of the coatings. EIS tests showed good efficiency of the Hybrid coating with impedance values up to $4 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for more than 68 days, due to the proper silica distribution in the DGEVA matrix. Enhanced adhesion and diffusion barrier can be achieved through silica incorporation, but its size and distribution affect the coating performance. The Hybrid system studied is the most promising for designing novel anti-corrosion bio-based coatings, but further structural optimization is needed.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A. Trentin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **E.C. Merino:** Methodology. **R. Samiee:** Methodology. **M. Parchoviatsky:** Methodology. **A.H. Pakseresht:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **A. Durán:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition. **Y. Castro:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **D. Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: [Dusan Galusek reports financial support was provided by EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation. Amirhossein Pakseresht reports financial support was provided by the Slovak Ministry of Education, Research, Development, and Youth. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal

relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper].

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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